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Role of Circumstantial Features in the Representation of Crime News Reports in Pakistani Newspaper “Dawn”

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Abstract

Circumstances play a significant role in providing details of the location of time and space, matter, means, manner, reason, purpose, degree, and accompaniment in the events of discourse. Using Halliday's model of Systemic Functional Grammar, this study aimed to analyze crime news discourse in the Pakistani English newspaper, Dawn, to figure out the significance of circumstantial elements. Circumstantial elements are used as instrumental in how news texts are used to represent, frame, clarify, or exaggerate crime events. As crucial textual elements, they have a vital role in contributing to the context of any clause in a particular text or a discourse. The UAM Corpus tool was utilized for data analysis. The results were interpreted qualitatively to determine the role of these circumstances in news reports. The findings of the study reveal that spatial locations are the most dominant circumstantial element (39%), followed by extent (18.6%), temporal locations (11.20%), manner (3.36%), cause (6.3%), matter (9.6%), accompaniment (10.99%) and source (3.51%). Spatial locations are frequently mentioned in the Dawn crime news reports, that clarify the place of crime happening. By highlighting the importance of circumstantial elements, this study advances a more comprehensive approach to discourse analysis. Media professionals may report crime events more justly and properly if they recognize the importance of circumstantial features. Consequently, it could influence public opinion and debate.

Keywords: Systemic Functional Grammar, Circumstantial, Crime news events, Representation

Introduction

Halliday's (2014) systemic functional linguistic theory, which provides an understanding of how language generates meaning, has had a significant impact on language studies around the world. More specifically, linguists may study human experiences through the language people use, the texts they create based on their prior experiences and ideologies, and the words they use to deliver a message, all because of the grammatical resources of an ideational metafunction. The crime news events reported by the reporters in newspaper reports can be categorized into distinct categories based on their representation, as they are reported by different reporters and hence affected by their different ideations and experiences.

The three primary elements that make up the ideational metafunction include i) processes, which are realized by the verb or verb phrases, ii) participants are the action's actors, which are realized by nouns and nominal phrases and iii) circumstances describe the where, when, how, why, for what purpose and on whose behalf the action occurs or executed. The present study focused on the circumstantial elements used in the news to portray the crime scenes. The most important circumstantial elements include place (both time and space), extent, matter, reason, purpose, behalf, contingency, accompaniment, and role. These have all been thoroughly examined in a variety of theoretical frameworks. The previous linguistic studies have not adequately addressed the aspects of projection of thought and locution. The present study seeks to ensure that the circumstantial features are correctly categorized at several levels, such as the word, sentence, and clause complex levels, to completely comprehend situational meanings. This study will employ Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar to examine how circumstantial choices influence the representation and portrayal of crime event texts at the clause and clause-complex levels.

Research Objective

The most important objective of the study was to investigate how newspapers use circumstantial evidence to portray news events and how the absence of this evidence affects crime events/reports representation. Another objective was to alert regular newspaper readers to a new method of understanding and interpreting the language used in newspapers. Resultantly, newspaper readers may become more critical of the language used in the news reports.

Research Questions

1. What is the pattern of circumstantial elements employed in the representation of crime event reports in the Pakistani English newspaper, *Dawn*?
2. What is the role of circumstantial elements in the manifestation of different types of crimes (e.g., major vs. minor crime) in Newspaper, *Dawn*?

Literature Review

Human communication relies heavily on language, which is a complex system. It enables the expression and exchange of concepts, feelings, and information through the use of spoken words, written characters, and non-verbal signs. Chomsky (1957) postulated that all languages share a universal grammar, demonstrating our fundamental linguistic capacity. Beyond its utilitarian applications, language is an essential cultural and social construct. According to Durkheim (1912), it preserves cultural legacy and passes on information to succeeding generations. It also represents common views and ideals. It is a dynamic system that is essential to human nature and culture. It shapes our beliefs, behaviors, and interpersonal interactions. Therefore, studying language is essential to comprehending human communication as well as the evolution of cognition and society.

Halliday (1994) asserts that language is a functional system, where meanings are made in the context. It is not merely a collection of rules of grammar.

According to Halliday (1994), language is a framework of subsystems and schemes for determining and analyzing word meanings. There has been a lot of research done by linguists on how speakers and writers use language to accomplish their goals. For their research, some have used systemic functional linguistics (Lukin, 2005). Systemic functional theory assists in determining the roles of words rather than only relying on their meanings or the use of rules inside a phrase.

In the field of systemic functional linguistics, circumstantial elements are important components of the clause. They add detail, clarity, and specificity to the clause (Qasim et al, 2018). For example, circumstantials of location clarify the settings of the crime scene; circumstantials of time specify the time of the incident; circumstantials of cause are important for determining the purpose of the incident; and circumstantials of means provide information

about the tools and weapons used in a crime. These are some of the reasons to concentrate on circumstantial elements. Despite their structural periphery and lack of importance as compared to processes and actors, circumstantial aspects significantly contribute to the context of any given clause.

Along with everyday occurrences like accidents and crimes, newspaper stories include political, religious, economic, social, cultural, and ethical topics. Though linguists contend that media texts are intrinsically biased and ideologically motivated, affecting public perception, readers frequently see these reports as objective (Archugar & Schleppergrell, 2005). News writings sometimes contain ingrained beliefs; hence they never accurately reflect reality. These biases can be exposed through a careful and systematic analysis. Linguists have recently studied how media texts expose biases and construct reality using a variety of methods, such as Halliday's transitivity (Lukin, 2005).

The circumstantial elements, according to Halliday and Firth (1957), determine the context for a process. They are identified through prepositions, adverbs, adverbial phrases, and occasionally nominal groups. They provide detailed information on various aspects of the context such as place, time, distance, frequency, methods, manner, comparison, quality, and degree, as well as reason, purpose, behalf, accompaniment, matter, and angle. Three of these major categories fall under the area of extent distance, duration, and frequency.

The "extent" of a process that is occurring now, has previously happened, or is going to happen, as well as how frequently the activity is repeated, can be determined by these variables. The "location" of a "process" in both time and space is described by its location circumstances (temporal and spatial location). "Location" can be absolute or relative, concrete or abstract, near or far, at rest or in motion, etc.

How a process occurs is known as the circumstance of manner. Means, quality, comparison, and degree are additional subcategories. The term "means" denotes the means utilized to accomplish a task. Using abstract words like honestly and sincerely to suggest quality refers to the quality of a process. A comparison circumstance aims to emphasize similarities or differences. The term "circumstance of degree" refers to using degree adverbs like "as much," "a lot," "extremely," or "heavily" to show the level or strength of an action or activity. The cause determines the reasons for implementing the process. The circumstantial elements of

cause and reason differ from Howard Jackson's Grammar by focusing on objective cause and subjective reason. The circumstance of behalf indicates the individual(s) for whom the process is occurring, while the circumstance of purpose indicates the motive or purpose for the process.

Contingency circumstantial features determine the variables that the process relies on. These can be categorized into three distinct subtypes. The factors that make it easier or harder to finish a task are known as the "circumstance of condition." Concession circumstances refer to reasons that were not accepted, indicated by words like although, regardless, despite, etc., and negative situations, indicated by words like unless, if not, and in the absence of. Default circumstantial elements represent negative situations denoted by unless, if not, in the absence of, in default of, etc.

The accompaniment suggests a mutual interest in a process. These circumstantials are divided into commutative and additive categories based on the "nature" of the "joint participation." A process with two elements that can be reversed is referred to as commutative, which is beneficial when the elements work together and harmful when they do not. The additive accompaniment results from two entities working against each other to achieve a common goal, as seen in the coordination of body parts when writing.

Guise and product classifications can affect the characteristics or value of an element. Guise is how an element is presented, while product is the outcome when an element transforms into a situation. The various circumstantials of a matter are shown "in relation to", "regarding", or "with reference to".

The study seeks to enhance comprehension of how media influence public opinion and support ethical journalism by analyzing linguistic choices. In Pakistan, how the media depicts crime strongly influences public perceptions and government reactions.

According to Abbas (2019), the Pakistani English media frequently exaggerates crime, leading to heightened public worry and responses of the controlling bodies. The method of portraying crime differs depending on the newspaper, editorial stance, and the reporter. Consequently, sensationalism and dramatic language prevail, highlighting the gravity of the crime rather than its root causes (Abbas,2019). Crime reports frequently do not provide a full social, economic, or political background, which can result in a distorted understanding of crime. Comprehending

these practices of media can promote ethical journalism and lead to a better-educated and well-informed readership.

This study aimed to examine, from a systemic functional standpoint, how is the representation of crime events in Pakistani English media. It investigates the language choices and framing strategies employed by newspapers to present crime, highlighting their influence on the public perception of crime and security in Pakistan. This study is grounded in combining pertinent scholarly works.

Previous Studies

Several significant research studies on Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) investigated the crucial role of circumstances in various discourses, some of them are as follows.

Burwan et al. (2018) studied the circumstances of the translation methods used to translate the Gospel of Matthew from English to Indonesian. The study found that translation methods like combination and equivalent can provide more precise translations. It emphasized how crucial suitable translation techniques are to producing excellent, culturally acceptable translations.

Isti'anah (2019) used Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar to study the transitivity processes in Seierstad's "The Bookseller of Kabul" which portrays the roles of Afghan women. The research shows the main portrayals of obedient and loyal female figures but it is limited by its small participant pool and concentration on a solitary piece of literature. It needs more extensive investigation.

Shah et al. (2019) analyzed crime coverage in Pakistani newspapers by comparing Daily Dawn and Daily Jang through a content analysis. Daily Jang covers a wider variety of crimes, while Daily Dawn primarily concentrates on urban crimes. Both newspapers covered similar cases of crimes against women and child abuse, shaping how the public views safety and crime.

Following Halliday's SFL theory, Abbas¹ & Talaat (2019) analyzed the selection of words embedded in the headlines of Pakistani English newspapers portraying crime against women. To explore the masked ideology of the media professionals they chose three newspapers including The Nation, Dawn, and The News. The analysis focused on the identification of gender-related attitudes towards men and women in the headlines and the roles associated with

them by the newspapers' authorities. This study also depicts how subtly the newspapers manipulate the reader's emotions to capture their attention as well as alter the opinion-making process of the target audiences.

Shi and Fan (2019) utilized critical discourse analysis and Halliday's transitivity approach to examine news articles on the "Belt and Road" initiative from Chinese and American media. The research shows different beliefs in how the program is depicted, highlighting the usefulness of transitivity analysis in revealing concealed beliefs in news coverage.

Asad et al. (2019) examined how Malaysian and Pakistani online publications cover the election, paying particular attention to how language might conceal meanings related to corruption. From May to July 2018, 25 news articles from both mainstream and independent publications were included in the study. The study emphasized disparities in the representations of social actors through the application of Halliday's transitivity analysis and Norman Fairclough's Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). Mainstream media displayed more political biases, but independent publications presented more objective and neutral images.

Heryono (2020) examined transitivity in early 2020 Indonesian COVID-19 news articles by employing the UAM corpus tool. The research analyzed the use of material, mental, and verbal processes, identifying significant shifts in their utilization. This study improves comprehension of how language adapts during emergencies.

Sahayu (2020) examined the depiction of Palestine and Israel in news stories from *The New York Times* and *The Jakarta Post* by integrating Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) with Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). The research showed variances in how things are depicted and presented, emphasizing the influence of language techniques on how readers view things. The study is enlightening, but limited by its small sample size and concentration on two news outlets.

Mahesar et al. (2021) studied the reporting of criminal activities in *The Nation* newspaper's Karachi edition throughout the year 2020. They examined 75 crime articles, honing in on different types of crime, characteristics of offenders, and reasons behind their actions. The research discovered a prevalence of crimes within families and emphasized the way Pakistani crime reporting covers and misses certain areas. The study is limited by sample size and an

emphasis on a solitary newspaper.

Al-Badawi and Al-Najjar (2021) conducted a comparison of BBC and CNN headlines on the Christchurch Mosque Massacre through transitivity analysis. They discovered that both agencies utilized experiential methods, with BBC preferring tangible methods and CNN employing more cognitive and interpersonal methods. The research shows variations in the way topics are presented and the language used by the two news organizations.

Isnaeni and colleagues (2021) examined how the Antara news agency employs experiential and logical functions to portray information and connections in a news story. Their examination showed that the article supported the government's viewpoints, especially regarding amendments to laws concerning the Corruption Eradication Commission. The research identified basic cognitive processes employed in the presentation.

To uncover underlying ideologies, Fallaki (2022) employed transitivity analysis to examine news reports on Russia's invasion of Ukraine. Through an examination of headlines from many foreign media, the research demonstrated how distinct transitivity patterns highlight diverse viewpoints of the war. The study highlighted how language shapes readers' comprehension and advocated for more open reporting.

Huda et al. (2023) used Systemic Functional Linguistics to assess the logical interpretations of texts regarding a judge's death in The Jakarta Post. They demonstrated how language structures reflect various semantic linkages in news coverage by identifying 16 different forms of logical relations.

Through interviews with sixteen journalists, Schott et al. (2023) investigated ethical standards in Pakistani journalism regarding domestic abuse. The study concluded that there were no official ethical rules and suggested that guidelines and training be improved to improve reporting processes.

Abunahel (2023) examined transitivity in the reporting of the Gaza crisis in 2022 by The Hindu and The Washington Post. This research showed disparate depictions, emphasizing how language shapes people's understanding of conflicts. The Hindu focused more on Israeli activities, while The Washington Post focused on diplomatic attempts.

Bartley (2023) looked into how the Central Park Five case was covered in the media, concentrating on transitivity patterns in stories from The Daily News, The New York Post, and The New York Times. The study highlighted the need for critical media literacy by demonstrating how media depiction led to the young men's erroneous convictions.

3. Research Methodology

This research employs circumstantial analysis as its methodological approach. The study assembled data from 100 crime event reports from Daily Dawn. The crime news reports data were converted to Unicode text files. The criteria specified a clause as the unit of analysis, and the methodology further entailed dividing each crime news event report into clauses and identifying the types of circumstances through circumstantial analysis, which included nine types and subtypes such as location, extent, manner, and angle among others.

These data were then incorporated into the UAM corpus tool. Based on that scheme, types and subtypes of circumstances were precisely identified, coded, counted, and calculated. The quantitative as well as qualitative approaches were utilized as the results of coding were to be collected from the software in the form of frequencies but the interpretation of results was qualitative. The texts were coded utilizing the scheme based on Systemic Functional Grammar's ideational metafunction. The results were then analyzed to decode the role of circumstantial elements in the representation of crime event reports as well as ideational meanings of language use and their relation to the portrayal of the crime event.

Data Collection

The crime news reports are taken from the newspaper *Daily Dawn*, 100 in number, from January 1, 2022, to December 31, 2022. The process of data collection includes the following steps: Each news report was copied from the source e-newspaper and pasted into a separate Word file along with the date of publication. After converting into Notepad files, each file was manually rectified by removing the symbols generated through data conversion software. These files were incorporated into the UAM software.

The UAM corpus tool was utilized for coding the text and calculating the frequencies and percentages of features. A well-developed scheme is employed for the software. Data are coded manually employing software to make the coding process more organized and systematic.

Circumstantials were coded, analyzed, and interpreted at the level of clause and clause complexity. The statistical results in the form of frequencies and percentages were collected from the statistics option of the UAM corpus tool. Then the frequencies of coded features were cross-verified using the Ant-Conc Corpus tool to ensure accuracy and reliability.

In the next step, the frequencies of various features were compared and contrasted across different crime news events to identify and interpret patterns of circumstantial elements and tendencies. The focus of the qualitative interpretation of the quantitative results was on the location, cause, matter, means, contingency, accompaniment, condition, and viewpoints communicated through the use of circumstantial elements in the flow of events presented in these crime news reports. The categorized features were interpreted in relation to their patterns and their impact on the presentation of crime events. The crime news report corpus was analyzed as per the following measures:

Annotation Scheme

Interpreting the Results Types of Circumstances Location Spatial Location

Table 1. Spatial Location; The Dawn News

Sr. No.	Spatial Location	Frequencies
1	In	384
2	On	00
3	At	52
4	To	85
5	From	49

The study has examined the role of circumstances in the text of crime news events. Table 1 presents a list of words as a spatial location. These words are given in the text explicitly with their frequency listed here in the table. From top to bottom, we have explored the categories of spatial location words like “In, To, At, From” with their highest frequent numbers. Here we have used an incident of crime report from Dawn News to prove how these specific words play the role of circumstances of location and contextual clues in the reporting of the crimes. First, the news report on the incident in North Waziristan which was published in the Dawn on January 1st, 2022, has used the lexical item “In” as a circumstance of spatial location. The reports provide a detailed account of four policemen and two killers/ terrorists who lost their lives for their ideologies; however, one terrorist (with weapons and ammunition) was arrested. Second, the news report of a bank manager sentenced “To” jail (published in Dawn June 18th, 2022), explains the usage of the word “To” as a spatial location of crime sequences.

Third, the word “At” has been used as the spatial circumstance to discover the crime event. It provides us with the contextual or situational clues of the event. In the incident of Mardan (published in. Dawn on July 8th, 2022), the circumstance “At” has been by the reporter to provide the information of the location where the security person was killed and three other officials got injured when a bomb exploded at the entrance of a check post in the area of Chamtar on Tuesday. Lastly the word “From” has been used as a circumstance to show spatial location in the context of crime in Pakistan. We have mentioned a tragic incident of a rape case, which was published in the Dawn for further detail. The officials reported that they had arrested a prime suspect in the case of a minor girl rape from the Chiragh Shah area of Lahore Cantonment on Tuesday. In another incident, a ten-year-old mentally challenged girl was allegedly raped and murdered by an unidentified person as published in Dawn on September 14th, 2022.

Temporal Location

Table 2. Temporal Location; The Dawn News

Sr. No.	Temporal Location	Frequencies
1	On	149
2	In	08
3	Till	03
4	Between	00

The highest frequency number word listed in Table 4.10 is “On”. It is a temporal location. The other words “In”, “On” and “Till” are circumstances of location. The table elaborates on crime events words/ processes and categorizes temporal locations using the crime events as reporters reported in Dawn News at different times.

The temporal locations “on” and “in” with frequencies 149, and 08 respectively have been used to elaborate on an incident of street crime published in Dawn. It further, reinforces the accuracy and authenticity of the analysis of temporal location. The incident in Quetta as published in Dawn on October 19th, 2022, illustrates the use of temporal circumstantial elements. It also elaborates on the CTD officials’ statement that four most- wanted terrorists were killed in an intelligence-based operation in Kharan, the area of Rakshan division on Tuesday. Further, the temporal word, “till” with a frequency of three has been analyzed in the context of crime news text. The incident in North Waziristan as published in Dawn on January 25th, 2021 illustrates the usage of the word “Till”. It is also a temporal circumstance that provides a criminal context (location) where five terrorists and two militant leaders were killed in intelligence operations in areas of Khaisur and Mirali (as officials said). The official report says that Rahim Shah was directly involved in terrorist activities from November 2020 to January 2021.

Extent

So Far; The Dawn News

Now we come to explain the use of circumstance of extent so far” with the help of a crime report published in Dawn on April 29th, 2021. The aforementioned incident occurred in Quetta in which a policeman was martyred and eight other people including three policemen got injured in a motorcycle bomb blast in Qila Abdullah on Wednesday. Sources revealed that no one claimed responsibility for the blast.

Distance

Table 3. Distance; The Dawn News

Sr. No.	Distance	Frequencies
1	Near	44
2	Nearby	10
3	Away	05
4	Along	16
5	Across	02
6	Throughout	00

Table 3 explains the extent-distance circumstance. The tabled words are distance categories of extent. They help to discover the distance between two entities. The table elaborates on the first extent-distance category “near” with 44 examples that indicate the distance between two entities in a crime context. The *Dawn* reports an incident in Gwadar where three FC cops got injured in an attack on the Khoshab Tehsil of Kech District on Thursday. The officials said that they were attacked by terrorists near the Shishan area of Khushabu, as per the report published in *Dawn* on May 7th, 2021.

The next distance category of the extent “nearby” has been used to investigate the incident of street crimes in the city of Quetta. Sources revealed that three people were shot dead in incidents in Kech and Panjgur districts on Monday. Levies officials stated that a boy was taken to a nearby hospital before being handed over to his family as per a report published in *Dawn* on May 4th, 2021.

Now we discuss the distance category “away”. It is also used in street crime news reports published in *Dawn*. For example, a tragic incident occurred in Karachi where a soldier embraced martyrdom in the South Waziristan district when an improvised explosive device was denoted on Monday. According to the report of the ISPR, during an intense exchange of fire, one of the terrorists was killed when he was trying to flee away. This very report was published in *Dawn* on August 31st, 2021.

The circumstance “along” with the occurrence of 16 used in news reports of *Dawn*, explains the relations between Pakistani crime reports and transitivity process types. Furthermore, the table unveils the “distance-extent” used in Pakistani news reports text. The “along” category of extent has been in an incident in North Waziristan/ Dera Ismail Khan. It highlights the

proximity in crime news report text. The report was published in *Dawn* on February 13th, 2023. The officials said that eight people including a woman got injured in a bomb attack on a vehicle carrying a wounded police official in the GK area along the border with Afghanistan. The circumstance “across” with two occurrences provides the textual and circumstantial explanations used in *Dawn* news reports, published at different times.

The table also helps us to understand the actual meanings of the text and context from the *Dawn* reports as well as tries to prove the viewpoint of the researchers that these enlisted words/ processes are closely related to the crime reports of Pakistani print media. The situational usage of the reports elaborates the tabled categories as distance type of extent circumstance. For example, as per the report published on 4th December 2022, three police officials were killed in an attack on the Akora Khattak area of the Nowshera district on Saturday. After that, the TTP asked its combatants to carry out attacks across the country. The aforementioned examples indicate the relationship of the category of circumstance, “distance” to comprehend the importance of spatial circumstance in the reporting system of the news media in Pakistan.

Duration

Table 4. Duration; The Dawn News

Sr. No.	Duration	Frequencies
1	During	69
2	Since	06
3	Recent	06
4	After	56
5	Ago	06
6	Yet	02

Table 4 explains “duration”, a sub-category of the extent of circumstance. It highlights its importance in the print media of Pakistan. The researchers have demonstrated their viewpoint of how the enlisted circumstances play an important role in narrating the Pakistani crime reports as well as an examination of their relevance regarding time durations of crime incidents. The word “During” given in the table has been analyzed as the duration in the process-context relationships context. It shows the relevance, time of action, and duration of the incident of the crime that occurred. For instance, an incident of the North Waziristan clash. According to the report published in *Dawn* on January 1st, 2022, four police personnel and two terrorists were killed during an operation launched by IBO.

The word, “Since” with its limited frequency evaluates the sequences of crime events. Along with other circumstances of location, time, and place it is associated with the categories of the process as well as the time frame of incidents. According to the Islamabad report that was published in *Dawn* on February 10th, 2022, the Chief of Army Staff Gen Qamar Javed Bajwa proclaimed the elimination of terrorists from Balochistan and all of the motherland. He said that numerous attacks occurred in the country since the last year and most of these attacks were carried out against the soldiers. The next category extent- duration encompasses the idea of the text-crimes relationship as well as studies the use of circumstance “Recent”. It has been used in *Dawn* news crime reports six times. The incident of the Quetta operation the aforementioned, where seven most wanted terrorists including two leaders were killed in Turbat as reported in the report published in *Dawn* on March 9th, 2022. The types of duration “After”, “Ago” and “Yet” with their frequency of 56, 06, and 02 respectively, evaluate the crime-text relations as well as the use of circumstance duration. As reported in *Dawn* on March 30th, June 20th, and October 26th, 2022, the incidents of Lakki Marwat, North Waziristan, and Dera Ismail Khan/ Lakki Marwat demonstrate the use of relations of these categories with crime events as well as their specifications of duration. All these examples indicate the significant role of the circumstance of “duration” in the context of crime news reports in the print media of Pakistan.

Frequency

Table 5. Frequency; The Dawn News

Sr. No.	Frequency	Frequencies
1	Once	01
2	Never	02
3	Few	04
4	Many	06
5	Least	14
6	Several	12

Different quantitative and qualitative aspects of the extent category “frequency” with its usage have been examined in the following discussion. Table 5 has listed six frequency types with their usage. Their number is twelve. The discussion includes an example from a news report published in *Dawn* on November 9th, 2022 to explicate these relationships and viewpoints. The Islamabad News reports remarks of the Interior Minister, Rana Sanaullah on the targeted killing of Arshad Sharif. According to him, the killing of mistaken identity has not been proven and

still there are several doubts. The given example explains the extent-frequency type “several” with its specific frequency numbers, as a basic word of crime reports published in the paper, *Dawn*. Furthermore, the table provides the frequency of this category in the given data to answer the circumstance of extent in the reports on crimes.

Manner

In a Befitting Manner; The Dawn News

The specific category of circumstance “Manner” with its limited frequency, provides validity to the discussion. The incident of Arshad Sharif's murder was discussed and reported by Islamabad news reporters in detail. the Interior Minister, Rana Sanaulah said that the killing had not been identified. He also said that the victim's vehicle was attacked in a very technical manner. Moreover, he said that the officials are doing their best and within no time they will be able to speak out the truth in front media and the victim's family. This report was published in *Dawn* on November 9th, 2022.

Means

Table 6. Means; The Dawn News

Sr. No.	Means	Frequencies
1	Through	10
2	Via	01
3	By	04
4	With the help of	03
5	Using	03

The circumstance of means elaborates on the subcategories “through, via, by, with the help of, and using” quantitatively. Table 6 shows their frequency. It also highlights the importance of circumstance of means in crime text creation. “Through” has the highest frequency. The example is found in the incident of a minor girl’s rape case in Lahore. The police officials said that they had arrested the prime suspect of the crime; however, another ten-year-old mentally challenged girl was raped in Chiragh Shah by an unidentified person. This report was published in *Dawn* on September 14th, 2022. It proves the stance that language items have a relation with crimes and a text can be elaborated only with the help of processes, circumstances, or logic-semantic relations.

Degree

Table 7. Degree; The Dawn News

Sr. No.	Degree	Frequencies
1	Huge	06
2	Large	07
3	Least	14

Table 7 deals with the circumstance of degree. It elaborates on the relationships between text and the context of crime. The table shows the importance of the circumstance of “degree”. This circumstance enables the highness of an action or process. The study aims to uncover the sub-types of degree and their relations in Pakistani street crime news reports published in Dawn News. As an example, the incident in Peshawar, Published in *Dawn* on September 24th, 2022. As per the report, six militants of TTP were killed by Pakistani personnel.

Cause

Reason

Another type of circumstance is “Cause-reason”. It speaks to the happenings’ elaboration and explains the hidden reasons for an incident. The study has identified the types of reason-circumstance as “because, due to, for” with their fixed frequency numbers 3,0, and 0. The study provides an example, published in *Dawn* on November 9th, 2022. The incident, “RSF seeks UN probe” presents the true exemplification of text-context (of crime) relationships as well as the importance of circumstance of cause-reason in establishing the news text of street crime discourse.

Purpose

The discussion uncovers the importance of “purpose” as a circumstance frequently used in *Dawn* News. The incident of TTP’s attack in the Akora Khattak area of Peshawar explains the circumstance of cause-purpose explicitly. It also elaborates on the researchers' viewpoint of text-context (of crime) relationships. The incident unveiled that three police cops were killed in this attack. This report was published in *Dawn* on December 04, 2022.

Behalf

The circumstance of cause-behalf is of utmost importance, which elaborates the text quantitatively. The word “against” has a frequency of 31. It explains how a single word can play a vital role in enriching a discourse of a language in any genre such as the crime events reports of “Dawn”. The incident of North Waziristan elucidates the text-context (of crime) relationship as well as the use of “against” circumstance as a sub-type of cause- behalf. The incident was published in *Dawn* on January 25th, 2021. It reports that five terrorists were killed in an intelligence-based operation in Khaisur and Mirali the areas of North Waziristan.

Matter

Table 8. Matter; The Dawn News

Sr. No.	Matter	Frequencies
1	Of	07
2	In	54
3	About	33
4	Regarding	01
5	Related to	01

The study uncovers the relationship between text and process, with special reference to the representation of an event and a circumstance. The aim is to signify the importance of these processes or circumstances in crime news data. It has examined how many times these words have been used in a crime report and the extent these circumstances make the language essence. The present discussion deals with the circumstance of “matter” precisely. This circumstance has already been explained in Table 8 quantitatively. The keywords of circumstance-matter have been written in the number of frequencies that explain the highness of a word/ category in text/ research data. The “about” a circumstance of matter with 33 frequency elaborates on the heartbreaking incident of Narowal published in *Dawn* on January 3rd 2022. The officials stated that they had arrested two persons on the charge of killing their friend. The aforementioned incident provides detail for the text and context of crime-closed relationships as well as evaluates the frequent circumstance of matter “about” category in Pakistani street crimes.

Accompaniment

Table 9. Accompaniment; The Dawn News

Sr. No.	Accompaniment	Frequencies
1	Also	55
2	Too	00
3	With	90
4	As well as	01

Table 9 presents the interpretations of the reports published in *Dawn* qualitatively as well as quantitatively. The section presents the objective and subjective results of the relations between crime reports with the processes, circumstances, and verbs/ word categories. It also unveils the circumstance of accompaniment in some detail. The study provides the sub-categories of “accompaniment”, also, with, and as well as” with the frequencies 55, 90, and 01 respectively. The frequency of these categories explains their richness and prominence in the data related to crime. The results show that if a text is missing any circumstance category the context will be irrelevant or far from the language source. The data represent a single example of accompaniment. The incident of Quetta elaborates on this circumstance where a police officer was killed as per the report published in *Dawn* on November 02, 2022. The example covers both aspects of the study as of the specific process/ circumstance relation with crime as well as the qualitative application of accompaniment circumstance in Pakistani street crimes for enhancement/ elaboration purposes to make the text more comprehensive.

Source

The discussion dives into the keyword “according to” a source category of angle. The circumstance has occurred 51 times in the crime reports published in the paper *Dawn*, which explains the relationship between circumstance and crime qualitatively. It also shows that the frequency and dominance of these types of circumstances carry importance in a crime text as they add comprehensiveness and meaning to the language. The Quetta incident provides an example of “according to” circumstance to represent qualitatively and reinforces the main idea of the study that the enlisted processes/ circumstances are closely related to crime reports of *Dawn* based on their frequent repetitions. The incident explored that four terrorists were killed and two police personnel martyred in an intelligence-based operation in the Harnai district as reported in *Dawn* on November 1st, 2022.

Conclusion

The current study aimed to clarify the important impact that circumstantial features possess on how crime events are reported in the Daily Dawn, a well-known English daily in Pakistan. This study has demonstrated different ways in which circumstantial features affect the overall framing, specificity, and clarity of news discourse by utilizing Halliday's theory of Systemic Functional Grammar.

The investigation shows that, despite being frequently disregarded in favor of actors and procedures, circumstantial variables play a crucial role in forming the narrative of crime reports. It has been demonstrated that providing crucial contextual information about place, time, cause, and means, among other things, improves the reader's comprehension of the crime events. For example, the locational circumstantials assist the readership in determining the crime scene's settings and place, while the temporal circumstantials pinpoint the exact time when the action occurred. Similarly, the circumstances of “means” and “cause” provide insight into the tools or techniques employed in the criminal acts, respectively.

Utilizing the UAM Corpus tool for data analysis, the study carried out a thorough qualitative investigation of the findings. The results imply that the role of circumstantial elements is crucial in creating the social reality that is presented in crime news events, impacting readers' perceptions of the incidents and the characters.

The implications of this study are significant for both linguistics and media studies. This study promotes a more thorough method of discourse analysis by emphasizing the significance of circumstantial elements—that are often neglected but key components of the clauses as well as texts. The study might help understand the contextual aspects of the texts. The media professionals might be able to report on crime events more responsibly and accurately, thus impacting public opinion and print media portrayal of crime events.

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